

**PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES
AND TEACHING METHODS
INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE**

2024

ISBN 978-955-3605-86-4

© Sp. z o. o. "CAN", 2024

© Authors, 2024

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference (17 September, 2024) - Copenhagen:2024. Part 37 – 180p.

Editorial board:

Tone Roald, PhD Associate Professor of Psychology University of Copenhagen

Elin Eriksen Ødegaard, Professor, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences

Mariane Hedegaard, Professor Emerita, Copenhagen University, Denmark

Magnus Englander, PhD Associate Professor of Psychology Malmö University, Sweden

Paul Sullivan, PhD University of Bradford Bradford, United Kingdom

Mathias Traczyk Søren, PhD

Thiesen Amanda, PhD

Nybroe Røhde, PhD

Languages of publication: dansk, English, русский, беларуская, limba română, uzbek,

The compilation consists of scientific researches of scientists, post-graduate students and students who participated International Scientific Conference "PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS". Which took place in COPENHAGEN on 17 September, 2024.

Konferencehandlinger anbefales til videnskabsmænd og lærere i højere læreanstalter. De kan bruges i uddannelse, herunder undervisning i postgraduate studier, forberedelse til opnåelse af bachelor- og kandidatgrad. Gennemgangen af alle artikler blev udført af eksperter, materialer er i henhold til forfattere copyright. Forfatterne er ansvarlige for indhold, undersøger resultater og fejl.

Conference Alerts
N E T W O R K

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS

Part 37
September 2024

Collection of Scientific Works

Copenhagen "Science Edition" 17 September 2024

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ОЦЕНКА ПРОВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ (IL-1B, IL-8) И АНГИОГЕННЫХ МАРКЕРОВ (VEGF-A И BFGF) В СЕРОЗНОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ ПАРАПРОКТИТЕ ЗИЯДУЛЛАЕВ ШУХРАТ ХУДОЙБЕРДИЕВИЧ КАМОЛОВ ЗАЙНИДДИН САЙФУТДИНОВИЧ ЖУМАНҚУЛОВ ҒАФУР АЛМАМАТОВИЧ	7
THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN TOURISM MURODILLAYEV BEKZOD VOXIDJON O'G'LI	9
GLOBAL DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT TRENDS ANALYSIS IN THE WORLD ECONOMY USMONOV JAMSHID RASULOVICH	11
SAN'AT VA UNING TURLARI MUHLISA BOZORBOYEVA AMONJON QIZI	16
БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФЛАРДА МАТЕМАТИКА ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШ МЕТОДЛАРИ ҲАМДА УЛАРДАН САМАРАЛИ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ МЕЪЗОНЛАРИ. ҚОСИМОВА НАВРУЗА ТАВАККАЛЖОН ҚИЗИ БОБАЕВА ЗИЁДАХОН МАХАМАДЖОН ҚИЗИ	18
MULOQOTNING TURLI VAZIFALARINI BADIY MATNLARDA QO'LLANISHI (FRANSUZ BADIY MATNLARI VA ULARNING O'ZBEK TILIGA TARJIMALARI MISOLIDA) МАМАЖОНОВА МУХАҲҲО МАХАМАДЖОН ҚИЗИ	23
МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ ТАШКИЛОТЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯЛАНУВЧИ АҚЛИ ЗАИФ БОЛАЛАРНИНГ МАКТАБГА ТАЙЙОРГАРЛИГИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ BOZORBOYEVA NIGORA ALISHER QIZI	26
SOTSIOLINGVISTIKANING TILSHUNOSLIKDA TUTGAN O'RNI JALOLDINOV MUHAMMADSAYID SARDORBЕК O'G'LI	37
GO'ZADA QO'LLANILAYOTGAN DEFOLYANTLARNING SAMARADORLIGINI O'RGANISH B.RAMATOV	41
ENERGIYANI ISTE'MOL QILISHDA AXLOQIY TARBIYANING ROLI MATKARIMOVA GULIRA'NO ABDULLAYEVNA	44
IQLIM O'ZGARISHIGA QARSHI KURASHISHDA BUYUK BRITANIYA TAJRIBASINI O'RGANISH. YUSUPOVA SOHIBA ISLOMBЕК QIZI	46
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA KUTUBXONA-AXBOROT FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA QARATILGAN TAJRIBA-	49

GLOBAL DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT TRENDS ANALYSIS IN THE WORLD ECONOMY

Usmonov Jamshid Rasulovich

*Deputy chairman of the board of private
joint-stock commercial bank “Davr Bank”
independent researcher*

Abstract: *this article explores the situation of the world's population using digital technology, highlighting their behavior in the digital environment and analyzing the economic indicators of certain IT giants in the world economy.*

Keywords: *digital environment, digital technology, internet, social network, mobile app, electron commercial, Facebook, Amazon.*

United Nations World Population outlook data show that 8.08 billion people now live in the globe. Since this time of last year, the world population has increased by 74 million people, which has a growth rate of 0.9 percent compared to the same period last year.

The number of unique mobile phone (smartphone) users was 5.61 billion at the beginning of 2024. Recent data from GSMA Intelligence shows that 69.4 percent of the world's population now uses a mobile device, compared to 138 million (+2.5 percent) more globally than in 2023.

Currently, more than 66% of all people on earth use the internet, with the latest data showing the total number of global users at 5.35 billion . Over the last 12 months, the number of internet users has grown by 1.8 percent, adding 97 million new users since early 2023.

An analysis of Kepios shows that active social media user identifiers exceed 5 billion, with the end user index equal to 62.3% of the world's population. Over the past year , the global total has increased to 266 million, with an annual growth of 5.6 percent (Table 1).

The proportion of mobile app users (69.4% per capita) was leading in Table 1, and the time users spent on the Internet was 6 hours and 54 minutes, and on social media 2 hours and 25 minutes ¹.

¹ DIGITAL 2024. It was developed by the author on the basis of his annual presentation about digital technologies in the world. <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2021-global-overview-report>

Table 1
Analysis of the state of use of digital technologies of the world's population (as of January 2024)²

№	<u>Specification</u>	2023 (mlrd. person).	In % compared to the total population	2024 (mlrd. person)	In % compared to the total population	Growth compared to last year	
						(mln. person)	in %
1	<u>World population</u>	8.01		8.08		74	0.9%
	<u>of which:</u>						
2	<u>Number of users of a mobile phone (smartphone)</u>	5.44	68%	5.61	69.4%	138	2.5%
3	<u>Number of internet users</u>	5.16	64.4%	5.35	66.2%	97	1.8%
4	<u>Number of users of active social networks</u>	4.76	59.4%	5.04	62.3%	266	5.6%

Social media is higher than the rest of the growth rate, i.e., it has grown by 5.6%. The growth of one of the best social networking sites of the process was noted in Facebook's 2023 financial report. The company's total revenue was US \$ 117.92 billion, the bulk of which is 24% more than in 2022, per revenue from advertising² (Table 2).

At the same time, the company's net profit grew by 35% to US \$ 39.3 billion. During 2022, Facebook users increased by 13% overall, while daily active users were 2.11 billion people. 2024-an average of 3.07 billion people use Facebook in a month³.

² <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks/charts/FB/facebook/financial-statements>

³ <https://www.macrotrends.net> analyzed by the author based on the data of the site.

Table 2

Facebook's annual revenue for 2013-2023⁴

Years	Annual income (mln.dol.)	Growth compared to last year %	Annual net profit (mln.dol.)	Growth compared to last year %
2013	7,872	154,7	1,491	4,7
2014	12,466	158,4	2,925	196,2
2015	17,928	143,8	3,669	125,4
2016	27,638	154,2	10,188	277,7
2017	40,653	147,1	15,92	156,3
2018	55,838	137,4	22,111	138,9
2019	70,697	126,6	18,485	83,6
2020	85,965	121,6	29,146	157,7
2021	117.92	137.17	39.3	134.8
2022	138.47	128.7	43.4	139.7
2023	142.98	136.1	47.6	134.3

In the Global digital environment, the majority of users of average statistical age (from 16 to 64 years old) are the reason for their internet appeals: search for information (63.0%); communication with loved ones and friends (56.3%); news and Information Awareness (55.6%); how to do this or that work (51.9%); watching videos, shows and movies (51.7%); search for new ideas (47.6%); search for products and brands (46.4%); education and course attendance (42.6%); place and vacancy search for travel (38.7%); search for information and tools related to health (36.3%); search for information about the formation of knowledge and skills about financial management(35.2%); play games (32.2%); business-related searches(30.7%); for acquaintance with new people (29.9%), they indicate⁵.

The Daily expansion of the content of digital technologies in the world economy opens up a number of new opportunities for entrepreneurial activity. As with traditional approaches to economics, the central issue of e-commerce approaches in the digital environment is “consumer attention”. While the internet environment is recognized today as the most optimal communication channel for entrepreneurial activity, the reasons why internet accounts or profiles are blocked can be considered as factors that prevent “consumer attention:

Excessive advertising on the internet (22.3%);

⁴ <https://www.macrotrends.net>

⁵ DIGITAL 2024. Jahondagi raqamli texnologiyalar haqida 2024-yil ko‘rsatkichlari. <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2021-global-overview-report> .

excessive number and bullying of ads (22.3%);
 excessive repetition of advertising (19.9%);
 the fact that advertising occupies the majority of the screen (16.7%);
 announcements are sometimes issued for the purpose of spreading the virus and
 lead to an error in the work of the ICT tool (16.5%);
 page load time multiplicity (14.6%);
 casting advertising before watching videos or shows (13.3%);
 avoiding offline and online ads from all sides (13.0%);
 exposure of ads to online privacy (11.2%);
 storage of personal data from use (10.5%) is like⁶.

Based on practical analysis of the world digital environment, the above factors have been formed due to the fact that Internet users are in a wide segment and various mechanisms of influence in the virtual world are not provided, although it is aimed at promoting segregation through the digital economy. Of particular importance in this is the selection of digital technologies and the development of implementation approaches to activities, depending on the different needs of digital users.

Many giant companies around the world are making extensive use of digital economy technologies. In particular, we can see the rapid development of digital technologies on the example of the Amazon company, which provides services only through the internet (Table 3).

Its annual revenue grew by 21.7% over the previous year to us \$ 469,822 billion, and its net profit rose by 156.41% over the previous year to us \$ 33,364 billion.

Table 3

Amazon economic indicators 2018-2023⁸

Years	Annual income (mln.dol.)	Growth compared to last year %	Annual research and development costs (mln. dol.)	Growth compared to last year %	Annual net profit (mln. dol.)	Growth compared to last year %
2018	135,987		16,085		2,371	
2019	177,866	130,80	22,62	140,63	3,033	127,92
2020	232,887	130,93	28,837	127,48	10,073	332,11
2021	280,522	120,45	35,931	124,60	11,588	115,04
2022	386,064	137,62	42,740	118,95	21,331	184,08
2023	469,822	121,7	56,052	131,15	33,364	156,41

To date, the global IT sector still remains a high-profile monopoly, with two types of monopolies-country and corporate, in both of which we can observe that leadership

⁶ O'sha manbaadan.

belongs to the United States. Most of the digital platforms are being developed and operating in the United States and from there they are spreading around the world. As for the second type of digital monopolies, there is a corporate, similar situation - most of the successful platform technologies are owned or controlled by several world corporations. For example, among mobile operating systems, monopoly leadership belongs to Android and iOS, among the manufacturers of database management systems, we can cite Microsoft and Oracle monopoly leaders, in sales - (Alibaba (B2B), Amazon (B2C), in transport - Uber) and others.

Thus, the global IT industry of digital platforms until recently was under the control of one state and several large corporations. The total capitalization of corporations whose business is based on digital platform technologies exceeds \$ 4 trillion, of which 72% fall to the United States, 22% to Asian countries, 4% to European countries, while being the largest consumers and users of platform ecosystem services. But the active development of the ideas of digitizing the digital economy and social life has changed the vector of development of the IT industry, where competition between developers and users of digital platforms began to appear and develop, and this has given a significant impetus to the development of the entire IT industry.

Taking into account the above, it is necessary to pay attention to local software in the existing geopolitical and socio-economic conditions, in the creation of new systems , especially in those areas that are important for the state and business, based on the requirements for ensuring national, economic, technological and other types of security.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. A.A.Abduvaliev, Digital economics: trends and perspectives (monograph)-T.: "Innovation development publishing-printing house" 2020.-190 B. ISBN978-9943-6730-5-2;
2. N.B.Yahyakhanov. Improving the use of digital marketing in enterprises (on the example of service enterprises). Diss. avt. - TSUE, 2023. – B.52.
3. Khodjayev S.M. Improvement of the e-government system in the conditions of the digital economy. Diss. avt. - TSUE, 2023.–B.53.
4. <https://ict.xabar.uz/uz/startap/big-data-texnologiyasi-va-undagi-malumotlarni-tahlil-etish>
5. <https://www.ibm.com/topics/cloud-computing>
6. <https://www.macrotrends.net>
7. <https://datareportal.com/>